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Abstract

Knowledge of coastal sedimentary dynamics is an essential tool in the sustainable management of high-value natural places, such as beaches, which play an important role in human life. With this aim, spatio-temporal variations of activity concentrations of the main natural radionuclides in intertidal sand samples were measured in order to analyse their role as tracers of different sedimentary processes on a beach with wide and diversified sedimentary dynamics (Las Canteras beach at Gran Canaria Island). The radionuclides studied were ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , ^{40}K and ^{210}Pb . A cluster analysis and a principal component analysis performed by using stationary averages of the studied radionuclides activity concentrations and other quantities, such as grain size and or bulk density, were developed. These analyses divided the beach into three zones of sediment distribution related to one of the main geomorphological characteristics of the beach. Finally, annual variations in $^{226}\text{Ra}/^{228}\text{Ra}$ ratios were used to study erosion and accretion periods on the beach.

Keywords Natural radionuclides; tracer; sedimentary processes; erosion/accretion

Taxonomy Natural Radionuclides, Beach Management, Beach Process

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Spatial variability

Temporal variability

Exposed beach

Beach near bar openings

Fully protected beach

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Spatio-temporal variability of natural radioactivity as tracer of beach sedimentary dynamics

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ABSTRACT

23 Knowledge of coastal sedimentary dynamics is an essential tool in the sustainable
24 management of high-value natural places, such as beaches, which play an important role
25 in human life. With this aim, spatio-temporal variations of activity concentrations of the
26 main natural radionuclides in intertidal sand samples were measured in order to analyse
27 their role as tracers of different sedimentary processes on a beach with wide and
28 diversified sedimentary dynamics (Las Canteras beach at Gran Canaria Island). The
29 radionuclides studied were ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , ^{40}K and $^{210}\text{Pb}_{\text{ex}}$. A cluster analysis and a principal
30 component analysis performed by using stationary averages of the studied radionuclides
31 activity concentrations and other quantities, such as grain size and or bulk density, were
32 developed. These analyses divided the beach into three zones of sediment distribution
33 related to one of the main geomorphological characteristics of the beach. Finally, annual
34 variations in $^{226}\text{Ra}/^{228}\text{Ra}$ ratios were used to study erosion and accretion periods on the
35 beach.
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53 **Keywords:** Natural radionuclides; tracer; sedimentary processes; erosion/accretion
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1. INTRODUCTION

As is known, natural radionuclides include primordial radioactive elements in the earth's crust, their radioactive progeny and cosmogenic radionuclides, which originate in the earth's atmosphere by interaction with cosmic radiation and detected on the earth's surface due to fallout. Naturally occurring radionuclides most commonly found on the earth's crust are primordial nuclides, mainly ^{40}K and the elements from the ^{238}U and ^{232}Th decay series. Concentrations of these elements on the earth's surface vary widely from one zone to another depending on their geology as well as other factors such as geochemical and geophysical conditions. The natural radioactivity of a beach is mainly conditioned by the composition of its sands and sediments, which originate from different rocks (with different radionuclide composition) that suffer weathering, erosion and subsequent transport by the action of different agents.

In recent years, numerous assessments of environmental radioactivity (not only of natural origin, but also of anthropogenic ones) have been developed in beach sands and marine sediments from different parts of the world (Abdi et al., 2008; Casas-Ruiz et al., 2012; Fares, 2017; Huang et al., 2015; Korkulu and Özkan, 2013; Malain et al., 2012; Pappa et al., 2016; Shuaibu et al., 2017). In most of these studies, the activity concentrations found for ^{226}Ra (from ^{238}U series decay), ^{232}Th and ^{40}K are on a comparable range among them. However, in some places like Miami Bay in Malaysia (Shuaibu et al., 2017), the northeast coast of Tamilnadu in India (Suresh Gandhi et al., 2014) and Cumuruxatiba Beach in Brazil (Vasconcelos et al., 2011), the activity concentration values are two orders of magnitude higher than in other parts of the world. In fact, in the radiological protection framework, the aim of the aforementioned papers, is radioactive background monitoring of beaches through estimation of radiological exposure to humans due to radionuclides in beach sediments. In this regard, external

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121 gamma dose rates and several different radiation hazard indices were estimated in Gran
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123 Canaria beaches, and any radiological risks were assessed (Arnedo et al., 2013).

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125 Furthermore, radionuclides in sediments have been used as tracers of different
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127 coastal processes including those related to dynamic processes on beaches. For example,
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129 ^{238}U , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K have been used as proxy of coastal heavy mineral resources or to
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131 estimate biogenic sedimentation (Ghosal et al., 2017; Gulin, et al., 2014). Also, particle-
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133 reactive radionuclides such as ^{234}Th , ^{210}Pb , ^7Be and ^{137}Cs have been used as tracers of
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135 sedimentary processes in order to determine sediment transport, sediment
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137 accretion/erosion or accumulation and mixing rates (Al-Mur et al., 2017; Carvalho et al.,
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139 2016; Du et al., 2010; Mahu, et al., 2016; Oguri, et al., 2012; Renfro, et al., 2016;
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141 Woszczyk, et al., 2017). It is precisely within this field of application of radionuclides
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143 that the aim of the present work is framed.

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146 The main objective of this paper is to analyse the spatial and temporal variability
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148 of gamma emitter radionuclides present in the intertidal beach sand in order to study its
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150 role as tracers of common sedimentary processes. For this purpose, we have selected a
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152 beach (Las Canteras beach in Gran Canaria island) with a diverse sedimentary dynamic,
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154 combining the characteristic dynamic of a closed beach with that associated with a beach
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156 open to wave action.

157 158 159 **2. STUDY REGION**

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162 Las Canteras beach is one of the most important urban beaches in Spain. It is
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164 located in El Confital bay (Medina et al., 2006), an important protected area north of the
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166 island of Gran Canaria, in the city of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (Fig.1). Las Canteras
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168 beach is approximately 3 km long, delimited by La Isleta Isthmus in the north and a
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170 breakwater (“Baja de Núñez”) in the south. This beach can be divided into three different
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172 sectors: the northern arch, the central arch and the southern arch (Fig. 1). Between the
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180 central arch and northern arch, there is a smaller sector, "Playa Chica," with physical
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182 limitations to the exchange of sediments with the rest of the beach. At high tide periods,
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184 tide currents are to the NE, while during low tide periods, they are SW. The wind direction
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186 is mainly NE, NNE and ENE due to the trade winds. During spring tides, the tidal range
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188 is greater than 2.5 m; during neap tides, it is approximately 1 m. The mean wave
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190 approaching direction is north and, during big storms, comes from the northwest. The
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192 average significant wave height is 1.42 ± 0.6 m, reaching up to 4 m in winter (Alonso,
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194 1993, 2005,).

197 As described in Alonso (1993), the sediments that compose the beach sand are
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199 thought to be provided by the Isleta Isthmus, La Ballena Ravine and the beach rock that
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201 can be found in different parts of the beach. Also, they could come from submerged
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203 sandbars that are located between the bathymetric curve of 50 m and the beachfront. This
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205 work explains that the sand across the beach can be considered medium and fine sands,
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207 with a size around 0.25 mm in diameter. The calcimetry and petrographic analysis of
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209 Alonso (1993), Alonso and Pérez Torrado (1992) and Medina et al. (2006), show that the
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211 lowest amount of organic matter appears on the southern arch of the beach. A
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213 geochemical analysis performed on two sand samples from the southern and northern
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215 arch, respectively, showed an enrichment in metal components (TiO_2 , Fe_2O_3 , MgO , V, Sc,
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217 Co and Cr) in the first one, while the organic sand (from north arch) presented higher
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219 amounts of K_2O , Na_2O , CaO , U, Sr, Ba, As and Th (Arnedo et al., 2013).
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222 In front of the beach, there is a natural rocky bar offshore that emerges during low
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224 tide. This bar neither closes the whole beach nor is a complete block as shown in Fig. 1.
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226 Instead, it is fragmented in different sections with openings between them. The first part,
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228 located in the northern arch, presents an opening between the "Barra Norte" and the
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230 "Barra Principal." This part of the beach is completely protected against wave action. On
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239 the south part of the “Barra Principal,” there is another opening, and the “Barra Amarilla”
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241 establishes the end of the protected part of the beach. The southern arch of the beach is
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243 completely exposed to the open ocean (Medina et al., 2006).
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246 The sedimentary balance and dynamic of this beach has been studied, especially
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248 since building and development near the beach. Different studies (Alonso, 1993, 1994,
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250 2005; Alonso and Vilas, 1996) indicate that the beach presents a seasonal variability with
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252 two different periods: erosion and accretion. According to these studies, erosional periods
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254 normally occur during intense storm events, so it is logical to expect them to occur during
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256 winter, while periods of accretion occur in summer. Furthermore, the beach has a different
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258 behaviour in its distinct parts due to the influence of many factors such as the presence of
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260 the natural offshore rocky bar and the type of sediments found on the different parts.
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262 During erosional periods, the southern arch loses a high amount of sediment that is
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264 transported longitudinally to the northern arch. During periods of accretion, sand from
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266 submerged sandbars is cross-transported to the beach so that the amount of sediment on
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268 the beach increases forming berms. Moreover, there are beach cusps formed on the
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270 northern arch during this period that can favor the presence of edge waves that generate
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272 longitudinal transport to the southern arch. Even though the sedimentary dynamic has
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274 long been studied in Las Canteras beach, there is still missing information about the origin
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276 and exchange of the sediment between the beach and the bay.
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278 279 **3. MATERIAL AND METHODS**

280 281 282 **3.1. Samples collection and preparation**

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285 Ten points were selected in each campaign for sand sampling (Fig.1). Four were
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287 located on the southern arch, one in the central arch, another one at Playa Chica, and the
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289 last four in the northern arch. In order to study any spatial and temporal variabilities on
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291 the radionuclides distribution along the beach, sand samples were taken monthly from
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298 September 2016 to August 2017 (120 samples in total). Moreover, pH, temperature and
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300 electroconductivity were measured at each sampling point. For this, a hole was made in
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302 the area of the square of each sampling point, digging until the water inside the soil
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304 emerged into the surface of the hole. Then pH, temperature and electroconductivity were
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306 measured from a sample of this water with a portable pH metre.
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309 In order to consider the marine dynamic influence, samples were collected in the
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311 intertidal zone during low tide. For each one of them a square of 1 m² was drawn on the
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313 sand at each sampling point and, after mixing them *in situ*, samples were taken from the
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315 superficial sand from about 0–5 cm depth. Once in the laboratory, they were oven dried
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317 at 80°C for 24 hours. After this period, they were taken out of the oven and sieved through
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319 a 1 mm mesh size sieve to homogenise them. Finally, samples were kept inside PVC-
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321 trunk conical containers filled to 40 cm³, then sealed with aluminium strips due to their
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323 impermeability to radon gas, and stored for approximately one month. This period was
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325 necessary to allow secular equilibrium between ²²⁶Ra and ²²²Rn.
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328 3.2. Gamma emission analysis

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330 The determination of radionuclides in sand samples by gamma spectrometry
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332 analysis was carried out using a CANBERRA Extended Range (XtRa) Germanium
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334 spectrometer, model GX3518, with 38% relative efficiency with respect to a 3” x 3”
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336 active area NaI (Tl) detector and nominal FWHM of 0.875 keV at 122 keV and 1.8 keV
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338 at 1.33 MeV. It works coupled to a CANBERRA DSA-1000 multichannel analyser with
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340 the software package Genie 2000 (Canberra Industries, 2006). Efficiency calibration of
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342 the system was performed using the CANBERRA LabSOCS package based on the Monte
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344 Carlo method (Arnedo et al., 2017; G. Guerra et al., 2015, 2017). Calibration was verified
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346 using reference standards for IAEA RGK-1 (potassium sulfate), RGU-1 (uranium ore)
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348 and RGTh-1 (thorium ore). Energy calibration was carried out using a ¹⁵⁵Eu/²²Na
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357 (Canberra ISOXSRCE, 7F06-9/10138 series) and confirmed using the 1460.8 keV line of
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359 ^{40}K (IAEA RGK-1) (Arnedo et al., 2017).
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361 The radionuclides of interest were determined from different photopeaks. ^{226}Ra
362 was determined from the ^{214}Pb using the 351.9 keV emission line. The ^{210}Pb was directly
363 measured using the emission line of 46.5 keV. The activity concentration of ^{232}Th was
364 calculated from ^{228}Ac by the emission line of 911.2 keV. This emission line was also used
365 to determine ^{228}Ra . Activity concentrations of ^{40}K and ^{137}Cs were directly measured using
366 emission lines 1460.8 keV and 661.8 keV, respectively. The counting time for each
367 sample was around 24 hours. Finally, the activity concentration of excess ^{210}Pb ($^{210}\text{Pb}_{\text{ex}}$)
368 was determined by the difference between the activity concentrations of ^{210}Pb and ^{226}Ra .
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378 3.3. Granulometric analysis 379

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381 Some aliquots were taken at each sampling point during the October 2016
382 campaign and a grain size analysis was carried out by dry sieving (Alveirinho Dias, 2004).
383 Around 100 g of each sample were used. The aliquots were weighed and passed through
384 five different sieves from 1 to 0.0625 mm at 1 ϕ intervals. Then, the portion retained on
385 each sieve was weighed separately. The results were analysed by the GRADISTAT
386 software (Blott and Pye, 2001).
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393 3.4. Statistical analysis 394

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396 A correlation analysis and two types of multivariate statistical analyses and were
397 performed to evaluate the spatial distribution of the activity concentration of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th ,
398 ^{40}K and $^{210}\text{Pb}_{\text{ex}}$, and its relations with other characteristics of the samples. The first
399 multivariate analysis used was a cluster analysis (CA). This analysis identifies and
400 classifies observations with similar characteristics within groups known as clusters.
401 Observations in the same cluster are considered similar to each other and different to the
402 observations in another cluster. Similarity is a measure of distance between any two
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414 individual variables (Ravisankar et al., 2014, 2015; Shaw, 2003) and, for this analysis,
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416 the Euclidian distance between the observations was used. Also, there are multiple types
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418 of CA and, in this work, the hierarchical CA was selected.
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422 The second multivariate analysis was a principal component analysis (PCA) or
423 empirical orthogonal functions (EOF) analysis (Thomson and Emery, 2014). This
424 analysis takes a number of variables and converts them so that they can be more easily
425 analysed, giving information about how variables relate with each other and identifying
426 different groups of variables (Abramson et al., 2010; Guerrero et al., 2016; Thomson and
427 Emery, 2014). According to literature, if the variance explained by the principal
428 components is equal to or higher than 70%, the fitted principal component to the data is
429 good (Ravisankar et al., 2014, 2015; Zhang et al., 2005).
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4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Activity concentrations

444 A Shapiro-Wilk normality test (Shapiro and Wilk, 1965) was performed on the
445 activity concentration values of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , ^{40}K and $^{210}\text{Pb}_{\text{ex}}$ in each sampling point. All
446 activity concentrations in all sampling points presented a normal distribution at a
447 significance level of 0.05, except for the activity concentration of $^{210}\text{Pb}_{\text{ex}}$ in sampling
448 point P9 (for this case, normal distribution was achieved at p-value < 0.03). The activity
449 concentrations of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , ^{40}K and $^{210}\text{Pb}_{\text{ex}}$ for each sampling point are shown in the
450 boxplots in Fig. 2. For ^{226}Ra , the activity concentration ranged between 5.4 ± 0.6 and 24.4
451 $\pm 1.4 \text{ Bq kg}^{-1}$ with a mean value of $13.9 \pm 0.9 \text{ Bq kg}^{-1}$; for ^{232}Th , it fluctuated between 6.4
452 ± 1.2 and $32 \pm 2 \text{ Bq kg}^{-1}$ with a mean value of $18.0 \pm 1.6 \text{ Bq kg}^{-1}$; from 52 ± 6 to $810 \pm$
453 40 Bq kg^{-1} with a mean value of $429 \pm 20 \text{ Bq kg}^{-1}$ for ^{40}K ; and between 12 ± 5 and $63 \pm$
454 6 Bq kg^{-1} with a mean value of $35 \pm 6 \text{ Bq kg}^{-1}$ for $^{210}\text{Pb}_{\text{ex}}$.
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475 A comparison of mean activity concentrations of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K obtained in
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477 this work at Las Canteras beach, and those values referenced for other coastal sediments,
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479 is shown in Table 1. When comparing the results obtained in both studies at Las Canteras
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481 beach, it can be appreciated that although the activity concentration values given in this
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483 work are slightly higher, the results obtained in both works are similar. The values found
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485 for Las Canteras beach are also similar to others found for Xiamen Island in China (Huang
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487 et al., 2015), in sediments from the Cadiz Bay in Spain (Casas-Ruiz et al., 2012) and for
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489 values obtained in Tema Harbour in Ghana (Botwe et al., 2017), being slightly higher for
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491 ^{232}Th . In other places, like Iran (Abdi et al., 2008), the Oman Sea (Darabi-Golestan et al.,
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493 2017) and the Yangtze Estuary (Wang et al., 2017), the values found for the different
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495 radionuclides are all slightly higher, except for the case of the ^{40}K in Iran, which has a
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497 similar value to Las Canteras beach. In other places like Tamil Nadu in India
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499 (Punniyakotti and Ponnusamy, 2018) or in Henties Bay in Namibia (Onjefu et al., 2017),
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501 the variability is higher, with values for ^{226}Ra being one order of magnitude higher than
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503 the value obtained for Las Canteras beach. In Brazil, it is possible to find places like Bahia
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505 Coast (Veiga et al., 2006) where the values for ^{226}Ra and ^{232}Th are one order higher than
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507 the values found in this study, but the mean activity concentration for ^{40}K is one order of
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509 magnitude lower than the values obtained in Las Canteras beach. The activity
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511 concentration values obtained in Cumuruxatiba beach, on the south of Bahia in Brazil,
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513 (Vasconcelos et al., 2011), correspond to dark sand and show much higher values in
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515 comparison to everywhere else. These variations are probably due to the different
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517 minerals that can be found in the different places aforementioned, manifesting the
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519 variability in activity concentration in different places, which is related to the variation in
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521 the components of the sediments. Finally, when comparing with the worldwide values,
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523 ^{226}Ra and ^{232}Th are below the world mean, while ^{40}K is slightly higher than the mean
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534 value given by the United Nations Scientific Committee on the Effects of Atomic
535 Radiation (UNSCEAR, 2000) for soil content.
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538 4.2 Spatial analysis 539

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541 When analysing the changes along the beach of the mean activity concentration
542 for each radionuclide, an increase in ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K is found from the southern to
543 the northern arch of the beach. However, for $^{210}\text{Pb}_{\text{ex}}$ this variation is not present, being
544 the value of activity concentration similar all along the beach except for P6 (Playa Chica).
545 This seems to indicate that the spatial distribution of $^{210}\text{Pb}_{\text{ex}}$ is controlled by a different
546 agent than the spatial distribution of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K . As it is explained in literature
547 (Al-Mur et al., 2017; Hülse and Bentley, 2012; Szmytkiewicz and Zalewska, 2014), ^{210}Pb
548 originates after the decay of ^{226}Ra , that produces ^{222}Rn , a short-lived gas that partially
549 diffuses into the atmosphere where it rapidly decays into ^{210}Pb . This fraction of ^{210}Pb is
550 adsorbed to atmospheric aerosols and deposited as fallout over the earth's surface leading
551 to unsupported or excess lead-210 ($^{210}\text{Pb}_{\text{ex}}$). According to the aforementioned
552 radionuclides, the main dynamic agents contributing to the spatial distribution of these
553 radionuclides could be related to wind for $^{210}\text{Pb}_{\text{ex}}$, and to waves and nearshore currents
554 that transport the sediments for ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K . However, the distribution of the
555 surface activity concentration of $^{210}\text{Pb}_{\text{ex}}$ is also influenced by the mixing or sediment
556 accumulation rates (de Carvalho Gomes et al., 2009; Palanques et al., 2017;
557 Szmytkiewicz and Zalewska, 2014). Thus, an analysis of ^{210}Pb activity concentration in
558 sediment cores should be performed to better understand the agents that affect the spatial
559 distribution of this element.
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581 In addition to activity concentration values, other quantities were also measured.
582 These include average grain size (ϕ), sorting, pH, conductivity (mS cm^{-1}), *in situ*
583 temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) and bulk density (g cm^{-3}) for each sampling point (Table 2). Temperature
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593 (T), pH and conductivity (EC) show small variation along the beach, so a loss of
594 radionuclides in a specific beach zone by chemical mobility between marine water and
595 intertidal sand seems to be dismissed, even though a further analysis should be done.
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600 A Shapiro-Wilk normality test (Shapiro and Wilk, 1965) was performed with a
601 significance level of 0.05 to quantities aforementioned and mean activity concentration
602 values of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , ^{40}K and $^{210}\text{Pb}_{\text{ex}}$ (averaging for each point and for all the
603 campaigns). The results indicate that almost all of them follow a normal distribution, since
604 all of them have a p-value > 0.05 , except for the grain size, which had a p-value of 0.02.
605
606 Additionally, a performed correlation analysis is shown in Table 3. All coefficients
607 correspond to the Pearson correlation coefficient (Ahlgren et al., 2003) except those
608 relative to average grain size where Spearman correlation coefficients (Siegel and
609 Castellan, 1988) were used. The p-value obtained for each correlation coefficient is also
610 represented, being that correlation coefficients are statistically significant when p-values
611 < 0.05 . Moreover, a strong correlation was considered when p-value < 0.005 .
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623 Strong positive correlations appear between activity concentrations of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th
624 and ^{40}K , and negative correlations between these activities and bulk densities of the
625 samples. The temperature of the sample and the grain size also presented a moderate
626 negative correlation with activity concentrations. Nevertheless, it is important to mention
627 that temperature correlation could be related to the sampling hour, as samples with higher
628 activity concentrations were systematically picked up earlier in the morning than samples
629 from the part of the beach with less activity. Conductivity and pH did not present a
630 significant correlation with the activity concentrations, which again suggest that the
631 chemical mobility does not influence the variations of activity concentration of ^{226}Ra ,
632 ^{232}Th and ^{40}K . Thus, temperature, pH and conductivity were no longer considered for the
633 rest of this study. In the case of $^{210}\text{Pb}_{\text{ex}}$, there is no significant correlation between this
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652 variable and the others. This seems to reinforce the idea that the main agents controlling
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654 the distribution of unsupported lead-210 are different than those controlling the
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656 distribution of the other radionuclides.
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659 Once the descriptive statistic was established, the CA was performed by using
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661 activity concentrations of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K . The dendrogram obtained from the cluster
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663 analysis is shown in Fig. 3. At a distance of 100, three different clusters appear; the first
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665 one with sampling points P1, P2 and P3; the second one with sampling points P4, P9, P5
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667 and P6 and the third one with sampling points P7, P10 and P8. The classification obtained
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669 almost agrees with the geographical distribution of the sampling points except for the
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671 second group, where sampling points of the southern and northern arch are gathered
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673 together. The explanation for this, however, can be found, if the location of the sampling
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675 points is analysed. The first group of points, which will be referred to as Zone I, is located
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677 on the part of the beach without a natural offshore rocky bar, therefore, the beach is
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679 completely exposed to wave action. The second group, which will be referred to as Zone
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681 II, is the one where sampling points are located near the different openings in the bar
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683 described earlier. The last group, which will be referred to as Zone III, includes the
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685 sampling points that are located in the parts of the beach that are fully protected by the
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687 “Barra Norte” and the “Barra Principal” on the northern arch. Therefore, the presence of
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689 the distinct parts of the offshore rocky bar seems to be one of the main influences in the
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691 distribution of sediment transport and accumulation of radionuclides along the beach.
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693 This behaviour, referenced at least for Zone I and III by Alonso (1993), could be
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695 interpreted as a validation of the role of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K as tracers of beach
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697 sedimentary dynamics.
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702 PCA results are shown in the biplot in Fig. 4. In this biplot, the first two principal
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704 components (PC1 and PC2) are represented with an explanation of the total variance of
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711 65.3 and 29.5%, respectively. On the one hand, activity concentrations of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th and
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713 ^{40}K present very small values of PC2, which means that the variance of these
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715 radionuclides is mostly explained by PC1 (Fig.4 and Table 4). On the other hand, variance
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717 of $^{210}\text{Pb}_{\text{ex}}$ is mainly explained by PC2 with factor loadings of 0.13 and 0.61, respectively
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719 (Table 4). This indicates that there is a higher correlation between the first three
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721 radionuclides, while $^{210}\text{Pb}_{\text{ex}}$ follows a different pattern. This agrees with the results
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723 obtained from the correlation analysis and, again, reinforces the idea that radionuclide
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725 distribution along the beach is controlled by different agents and origins. Hence, the
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727 marine sedimentary dynamic could control ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K distribution while other
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729 causes, such as the aeolian sedimentary dynamic, would be the one controlling the
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731 distribution of $^{210}\text{Pb}_{\text{ex}}$. In addition, the inverse correlation that exists between the grain
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733 size and the bulk density of the sample with the activity concentration of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th and
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735 ^{40}K is also represented. However, grain size values are given in the ϕ scale and this scale
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737 is opposite to metrics (Krumbein, 1934). Therefore, higher values in ϕ units indicate
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739 sediments are finer, thus, grain sizes and activity concentrations are directly correlated.
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743 Moreover, Fig. 4 also exhibits the scores that the sampling locations obtained on
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745 the PCA. These scores give an idea of how the observations are grouped and how they
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747 relate with the different variables. Results for ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K are mostly influenced
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749 by PC1, and three groups can be defined along this axis. The first group shows negative
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751 values of PC1 and includes sampling points P1, P2 and P3, all of them with the lowest
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753 activity concentration values of these radionuclides (Fig. 2). The second group includes
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755 all sampling points located around zero in the PC1 axis. These sampling points are P4,
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757 P5 and P9, all of them with intermediate activity concentrations. The third group refers
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759 to sampling points P7, P8 and P10. All of them present positive values in PC1 and their
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761 activity concentration values are the highest. The distribution of the sampling locations is
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770 slightly different from the one shown in Fig.3, but it follows the same general pattern.
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772 Sampling points P1, P2 and P3 (Zone I) corresponds to negative values of PC1, sampling
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774 points P4, P5 and P9 (Zone II) are located close to zero values of PC1 and sampling
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776 stations P7, P8 and P10 (Zone III) show the higher values in PC1. The only exception is
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778 sampling point P6, located in a very particular place (mentioned in Section 2), so it could
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780 be under the influence of other variables.
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783 Focusing on the second eigenvector (PC2), it mostly explains the variance
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785 associated with $^{210}\text{Pb}_{\text{ex}}$, as was pointed out, perhaps mainly driven by aerosol dynamics.
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787 This component splits Zone II into two groups. On the one hand, the lowest values of PC2
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789 correspond to sampling points P6 and P9, which present lower activity concentrations of
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791 this radionuclide (Fig. 2). Specifically, sampling P6 is in an area of the beach that is well
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793 protected against wind action, which could explain the lowest values of $^{210}\text{Pb}_{\text{ex}}$ for that
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795 location (not only of Zone II, but for the entire beach). Opposite behaviour is followed by
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797 sampling stations P4 and P5, which show higher values of PC2 as a result of their $^{210}\text{Pb}_{\text{ex}}$
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799 activity concentrations higher than P6 and P9. However, the obtained values for P4 and
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801 P5 are of the same order as the ones obtained for $^{210}\text{Pb}_{\text{ex}}$ in the rest of the beach. In other
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803 words, sampling points from Zone II scored mainly on PC2, while the rest scored mostly
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805 on PC1 (except P8 with similar scores in both PC1 and PC2). In view of the above, as
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807 well as PC1 and PC2 percentages of total variance, one could say that the influence of
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809 ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K on sedimentary dynamics of Zones I and III is more of a determining
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811 factor than in Zone II where other dynamical agents could be considered.
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815 Moreover, Zone I shows the lowest values in activity concentration of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th
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817 and ^{40}K , as well as in grain size (highest in ϕ units) and the highest in bulk density.
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819 Sediments in this area are fine sands (0.177 mm average size) with a high proportion of
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821 metal components. Bulk density values respond to the sediment density, and therefore, to
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829 their composition. In this area, most common sediments are heavy-metal oxides (mostly
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832 whose densities are 5.18, 4.75 and 3.3 g cm⁻³ for magnetite, ilmenite, and pyroxenes,
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834 respectively. On the other hand, the most common material at the northern sector of the
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836 beach (sampling points P7, P8 and P10, Zone III) are bioclastic sands (0.215 mm average
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838 size) rich in calcite and aragonite with a density of 2.75 and 2.93 g cm⁻³, respectively,
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840 and, according to what was stated in Section 2, with higher proportions of K₂O, as well
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842 as of Th and U, than Zone I. This agrees with the fact that samples collected from Zone
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844 I, where the mineral composition is dominant, shows lower activities of ²³²Th, ²²⁶Ra and
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846 ⁴⁰K and higher bulk density. The scores obtained by samples from Zone III, samples of
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848 more calcareous and organic origin, are opposite to those from Zone I, pointing out that
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850 these samples have lower mass and higher activity concentration.
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854 4.4 Temporal analysis

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857 Dai et al. (2011) suggested the use of the ratio ²²⁶Ra/²²⁸Ra as a tracer for erosion
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859 and accretion periods in a marine environment. According to them, ²²⁸Ra and ²²⁶Ra are
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861 more present in the crystal framework of clay minerals, but the carbonate and
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863 exchangeable phases contain more ²²⁸Ra. Thus, accretion or erosion periods could be
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865 measured by a change in the ratio between ²²⁶Ra and ²²⁸Ra. Hence, during accretion
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867 periods, the input of ²²⁸Ra would be higher and the value of the ratio would be less than
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869 1 (i.e., the natural ratio of ²³²Th/²³⁸U was assumed); a value higher than 1 would indicate
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871 an erosional period. Some crystals from clay minerals and zeolites have been found in the
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873 north of Las Canteras beach, (Mangas and Julià-Miralles, 2015). Therefore, this ratio
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875 could be used to perform the temporal analysis. Moreover, as the spatial analysis
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877 presented three different sectors along the beach, that could be related to different
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879 dynamic behaviour, the analysis was performed in each one of these zones.
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Fig. 5 shows the results after applying the $^{226}\text{Ra}/^{228}\text{Ra}$ ratio to the three zones of the beach. Zone III is the area that is fully protected by the natural offshore rocky bar, and all values are lower than 1. This would indicate that Zone III presented a constant accretion during the whole study period. Moreover, from March 2017 to August 2017, there seems to be a decrease in the ratio values, compared to the values obtained in October and December 2016, suggesting a more intense accretion of sediments during the first mentioned period.

Zone II is the part of the beach located opposite to the openings of the calcarenitic bar, so it is likely to have a more complex dynamic. Two periods could be differentiated. The first one occurs from September 2016 through February 2017, when values of $^{226}\text{Ra}/^{228}\text{Ra}$ ratio were around 1, indicating small changes in sediment volume. The second period occurs from March through August 2017, and the ratio is clearly less than 1, suggesting accretion, which should be stronger in July and August.

In Zone I, September 2016 and February 2017 present $^{226}\text{Ra}/^{228}\text{Ra}$ ratios around 1.25, indicating strong erosion, while October 2016 and July 2017 show $^{226}\text{Ra}/^{228}\text{Ra}$ ratios around 0.75, indicating strong deposition. The rest of the months have values around 1. The strong variability suggests that the processes of erosion and accretion in this area are stronger than in the others, involving large amount of sediments that are moved away in the case of erosion and accumulated in the case of accretion.

Unfortunately, we do not have data of volume changes along the beach for the same study period, which could be used to confirm or discard what has been inferred from $^{226}\text{Ra}/^{228}\text{Ra}$ ratios. Nevertheless, previous studies in this beach point out that Zone III presents a clear accumulative trend in the long term, Zone II shows much lower volume changes because of the presence of a rocky substratum that is present all along this area, and Zone I presents a very strong seasonal variability, consisting of erosive periods during

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947 winter followed by strong accretion during summer (Alonso, 1993; Alonso and Vilas,
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949 1996). Obtained ratios of $^{226}\text{Ra}/^{228}\text{Ra}$ seem to confirm the accretion at Zone III, certain
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951 seasonal changes at Zone II and strong changes at Zone I. However, further studies with
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953 longer time series are necessary to better understand the temporal variability of the
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955 environmental radioactivity of the beach, and to get a better correlation with the
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957 sedimentary dynamics at this beach. In addition to testing whether the decision value for
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959 the $^{226}\text{Ra}/^{228}\text{Ra}$ ratio is 1 or somewhat lower, depends on more adequate average natural
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961 $^{232}\text{Th}/^{238}\text{U}$ ratio in Las Canteras.

964 5. CONCLUSIONS

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967 The analysis of spatial and temporal variations of activity concentrations of ^{226}Ra ,
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969 ^{232}Th and ^{40}K of intertidal sand samples seems to indicate its feasibility to trace different
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971 characteristic processes of the sedimentary dynamics at Las Canteras beach (which
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973 involves typical dynamics of both a wave action protected beach and one open to this
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975 action).

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977 A CA and a PCA were carried out to evaluate the spatial variability of activity
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979 concentrations, showing that sampling points are grouped in three zones with activity
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981 concentration values conditioned by the morphology of the natural offshore rocky bar.
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983 Thus, the sampling points that are not influenced by the rocky bar correspond to Zone I
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985 and present the lowest activity concentrations of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K . Zone II includes
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987 sampling points that are located near the different openings in the bar. Being that this
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989 zone is partially protected from wave action, it presents intermediate values of activity
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991 concentrations. Finally, Zone III refers to sampling points that are in parts of the beach
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993 that are fully protected by the “Barra Norte” and “Barra Principal” on the northern arch.
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995 Sampling points in this area present the highest values in activity concentration.
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997 Therefore, it seems viable that ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K can be used as tracers of the
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1006 distribution of sediments along the beach based on the different marine dynamics related
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1008 to the morphology of the offshore rocky bar at Las Canteras beach.
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1010 The temporal analysis was performed by mean of the ratio $^{226}\text{Ra}/^{228}\text{Ra}$ in order to
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1012 evaluate erosion and accretion of sediment periods along the beach. The results suggest
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1014 that Zones I and II could be affected by either erosion or accretion, while Zone III shows
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1016 a steady accretionary process, which agrees with previous studies at Las Canteras beach.
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1018 However, a longer-term study would be necessary to better understand the relation
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1020 between temporal variability of the environmental radioactivity and beach erosion/
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1022 accretion periods.
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1025 Finally, the use of these natural radionuclides as tracers of the different
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1027 sedimentary dynamics of Las Canteras beach could provide useful information for beach
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1029 anthropogenic management, as well as to control and manage any spills that may occur
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1031 near the beach. Moreover, this study could easily be extended to the management of other
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1033 beaches of similar sedimentary dynamics.
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Fig. 1. Location, division and sampling points on Las Canteras beach. Coordinates are in the UTM system.

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Fig. 2. Boxplots of the activity concentrations found for each sampling point for ²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th, ⁴⁰K and ²¹⁰Pb_{ex}. The dash line indicates the mean activity concentration value. The numbers that appear in each whisker correspond to the maximum and minimum activity concentration values. The number in the middle indicates the mean activity concentration value for each sampling point.

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Fig. 3. Dendrogram showing clustering for the different sampling points based on their activity concentrations of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K .

Fig. 4. Biplot of loading plot with the eigenvectors obtained for the grain size in the phi scale (Size ϕ), sorting, mass of the sample and activity concentrations of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , ^{40}K and $^{210}\text{Pb}_{\text{ex}}$ (blue axes) and scores of observations (black axes).

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Fig. 5. Mean $^{226}\text{Ra}/^{228}\text{Ra}$ ratios for each campaign in each zone of Las Canteras beach. Dash lines correspond to value 1 for the ratio.

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Table 1

Comparison of activity concentrations (Bq kg⁻¹) of ²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th and ⁴⁰K of Las Canteras beach sand and beach sand and marine sediments from coastal zones of other countries around the world.

Location	²²⁶ Ra		²³² Th		⁴⁰ K		Reference
	Range	Mean	Range	Mean	Range	Mean	
Las Canteras (Spain)	5.4–24.4	13.9	6.4–32	18.0	52–810	429	This work
Las Canteras (Spain)	7–19	14	7–25	15	83–629	390	Arnedo et al., 2013
Xiamen Island (China)	7.9–25.7	14.6	6.7–41.4	10.9	197.4–421.3	396.4	Huang et al., 2015
Cumuruxatiba (Brazil)	7050–8320	7810	17630–18450	17770	2220–3110	2660	Vasconcelos et al., 2011
Persian Gulf (Iran)	17–48	35	15–45	26	146–500	395	Abdi et al., 2008
Sediments of Cadiz Bay (Spain)	3–41	13	3–73	19	105–1342	451	Casas-Ruiz et al., 2012
Oman sea (Arabic Gulf)	8–55	28	5–42	22	250–980	640	Darabi-Golestan et al., 2017
Tema Harbour (Ghana)	-	14	-	30	-	325	Botwe et al., 2017
Henties Bay (Namibia)	25.32–235.55	175.59	BDL–77.99	40.17	222.39–482.16	349.66	Onjefu et al., 2017
Bahia Coast (Brazil)	10–572	184	14–173	533	25–62	42	Veiga et al., 2006
Tamil Nadu Coast (India)	BDL–370.77	12.3	BDL–3773.6	59.03	BDL–525.9	197.03	Punniyakotti and Ponnusamy, 2018
Yangtze Estuary (China)	13.7–52.3	24.3	26.1–71.9	40.9	392–898	628	Wang et al., 2017
Worldwide		32		45		420	UNSCEAR, 2000

BDL = Below detection limit.

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Table 2

Non-radioactive data and results obtained from granulometric analysis of the samples from Las Canteras beach. Mean values for pH, conductivity (EC), temperature (T), bulk density (ρ) of the sample, grain size in ϕ units, sorting, skewness and the classification of the samples depending on granulometric parameters are included.

Sampling point	pH	EC	T	ρ	Grain size	Sorting	Skewness	Classification		
		mS cm ⁻¹	°C	g cm ⁻³	ϕ	ϕ	ϕ	Grain size	Sorting	Skewness
P1	8.09	54.03	21.25	2.030	2.532	0.414	0.141	Fine Sand	Well Sorted	Fine Skewed
P2	8.05	57.26	21.04	2.025	2.521	0.401	0.125	Fine Sand	Well Sorted	Fine Skewed
P3	8.17	57.72	20.82	1.945	2.449	0.450	-0.168	Fine Sand	Well Sorted	Coarse Skewed
P4	7.99	55.07	20.53	1.830	2.186	0.601	-0.230	Fine Sand	Moderately Well Sorted	Coarse Skewed
P5	8.13	56.92	20.42	1.812	2.304	0.623	-0.260	Fine Sand	Moderately Well Sorted	Coarse Skewed
P6	8.14	56.58	20.45	1.826	1.437	0.900	0.039	Medium Sand	Moderately Sorted	Symmetrical
P7	8.12	57.20	20.47	1.671	2.049	0.671	-0.211	Fine Sand	Moderately Well Sorted	Coarse Skewed
P8	8.24	56.80	20.30	1.712	2.409	0.470	-0.192	Fine Sand	Well Sorted	Coarse Skewed
P9	8.27	56.83	20.32	1.812	2.202	0.591	-0.268	Fine Sand	Moderately Well Sorted	Coarse Skewed
P10	8.13	55.95	20.60	1.668	2.194	0.586	-0.246	Fine Sand	Moderately Well Sorted	Coarse Skewed

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Table 3

Correlation coefficients matrix of activity concentrations of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , ^{40}K , $^{210}\text{Pb}_{\text{ex}}$, pH, electroconductivity (EC), temperature (T), grain size in the ϕ scale, sorting and, bulk density (ρ) of samples. Correlation coefficients are shown in the bottom left diagonal and p-value at the top right diagonal in cursive.

	^{226}Ra	^{232}Th	^{40}K	$^{210}\text{Pb}_{\text{ex}}$	pH	EC	T	Size	Sorting	ρ
^{226}Ra	1	<i>0.000</i>	<i>0.000</i>	<i>0.312</i>	<i>0.489</i>	<i>0.294</i>	<i>0.017</i>	<i>0.016</i>	<i>0.143</i>	<i>0.000</i>
^{232}Th	0.972	1	<i>0.000</i>	<i>0.251</i>	<i>0.577</i>	<i>0.518</i>	<i>0.051</i>	<i>0.033</i>	<i>0.219</i>	<i>0.000</i>
^{40}K	0.979	0.980	1	<i>0.242</i>	<i>0.418</i>	<i>0.490</i>	<i>0.015</i>	<i>0.043</i>	<i>0.189</i>	<i>0.000</i>
$^{210}\text{Pb}_{\text{ex}}$	0.357	0.401	0.408	1	<i>0.615</i>	<i>0.903</i>	<i>0.603</i>	<i>0.960</i>	<i>0.326</i>	<i>0.245</i>
pH	0.249	0.201	0.289	-0.182	1	<i>0.200</i>	<i>0.161</i>	<i>0.855</i>	<i>0.935</i>	<i>0.366</i>
EC	0.369	0.233	0.248	-0.045	0.443	1	<i>0.258</i>	<i>0.651</i>	<i>0.776</i>	<i>0.567</i>
T	-0.730	-0.629	-0.736	-0.188	-0.479	-0.395	1	<i>0.187</i>	<i>0.071</i>	<i>0.005</i>
Size	-0.733	-0.673	-0.648	-0.018	-0.067	0.164	0.455	1	<i>0.000</i>	<i>0.077</i>
Sorting	0.498	0.427	0.452	-0.347	0.030	0.103	-0.592	-0.903	1	<i>0.149</i>
ρ	-0.960	-0.948	-0.985	-0.406	-0.321	-0.207	0.810	0.584	-0.492	1

*p = 0.000 corresponds to p < 0.005 (strong correlation)

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Table 4

Factor loadings of radiological variables on three significant principal components. Percentage of variance explained by each principal component and their cumulative percentage of total variance are also given.

Variables	PC1	PC2	PC3
²²⁶ Ra	0.46	0.09	-0.19
²³² Th	0.45	0.14	-0.26
⁴⁰ K	0.46	0.13	-0.18
²¹⁰ Pb _{ex}	0.13	0.61	0.75
Size	-0.27	0.56	-0.21
Sorting	0.30	-0.50	0.51
Bulk density	-0.45	-0.11	0.05
% of Variance	65.3	29.5	3.9
Cumulative %	65.3	94.8	98.7

Fig. 1. Location, division and sampling points on Las Canteras beach. Coordinates are in the UTM system.

Fig. 2. Boxplots of the activity concentrations found for each sampling point for ²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th, ⁴⁰K and ²¹⁰Pb_{ex}. The dash line indicates the mean activity concentration value. The numbers that appear in each whisker correspond to the maximum and minimum activity concentration values. The number in the middle indicates the mean activity concentration value for each sampling point.

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Table 1

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Tema Harbour (Ghana)	-	14	-	30	-	325	Botwe et al., 2017
Henties Bay (Namibia)	25.32–235.55	175.59	BDL–77.99	40.17	222.39–482.16	349.66	Onjefu et al., 2017
Bahia Coast (Brazil)	10–572	184	14–173	533	25–62	42	Veiga et al., 2006
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Table 2

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Sampling point	pH	EC	T	ρ	Grain size	Sorting	Skewness	Classification		
		mS cm ⁻¹	°C	g cm ⁻³	ϕ	ϕ	ϕ	Grain size	Sorting	Skewness
P1	8.09	54.03	21.25	2.030	2.532	0.414	0.141	Fine Sand	Well Sorted	Fine Skewed
P2	8.05	57.26	21.04	2.025	2.521	0.401	0.125	Fine Sand	Well Sorted	Fine Skewed
P3	8.17	57.72	20.82	1.945	2.449	0.450	-0.168	Fine Sand	Well Sorted	Coarse Skewed
P4	7.99	55.07	20.53	1.830	2.186	0.601	-0.230	Fine Sand	Moderately Well Sorted	Coarse Skewed
P5	8.13	56.92	20.42	1.812	2.304	0.623	-0.260	Fine Sand	Moderately Well Sorted	Coarse Skewed
P6	8.14	56.58	20.45	1.826	1.437	0.900	0.039	Medium Sand	Moderately Sorted	Symmetrical
P7	8.12	57.20	20.47	1.671	2.049	0.671	-0.211	Fine Sand	Moderately Well Sorted	Coarse Skewed
P8	8.24	56.80	20.30	1.712	2.409	0.470	-0.192	Fine Sand	Well Sorted	Coarse Skewed
P9	8.27	56.83	20.32	1.812	2.202	0.591	-0.268	Fine Sand	Moderately Well Sorted	Coarse Skewed
P10	8.13	55.95	20.60	1.668	2.194	0.586	-0.246	Fine Sand	Moderately Well Sorted	Coarse Skewed

Table 3

Correlation coefficients matrix of activity concentrations of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , ^{40}K , $^{210}\text{Pb}_{\text{ex}}$, pH, electroconductivity (EC), temperature (T), grain size in the ϕ scale, sorting and, bulk density (ρ) of samples. Correlation coefficients are shown in the bottom left diagonal and p-value at the top right diagonal in cursive.

	^{226}Ra	^{232}Th	^{40}K	$^{210}\text{Pb}_{\text{ex}}$	pH	EC	T	Size	Sorting	ρ
^{226}Ra	1	<i>0.000</i>	<i>0.000</i>	<i>0.312</i>	<i>0.489</i>	<i>0.294</i>	<i>0.017</i>	<i>0.016</i>	<i>0.143</i>	<i>0.000</i>
^{232}Th	0.972	1	<i>0.000</i>	<i>0.251</i>	<i>0.577</i>	<i>0.518</i>	<i>0.051</i>	<i>0.033</i>	<i>0.219</i>	<i>0.000</i>
^{40}K	0.979	0.980	1	<i>0.242</i>	<i>0.418</i>	<i>0.490</i>	<i>0.015</i>	<i>0.043</i>	<i>0.189</i>	<i>0.000</i>
$^{210}\text{Pb}_{\text{ex}}$	0.357	0.401	0.408	1	<i>0.615</i>	<i>0.903</i>	<i>0.603</i>	<i>0.960</i>	<i>0.326</i>	<i>0.245</i>
pH	0.249	0.201	0.289	-0.182	1	<i>0.200</i>	<i>0.161</i>	<i>0.855</i>	<i>0.935</i>	<i>0.366</i>
EC	0.369	0.233	0.248	-0.045	0.443	1	<i>0.258</i>	<i>0.651</i>	<i>0.776</i>	<i>0.567</i>
T	$\bar{-}$ 0.730	$\bar{-}$ 0.629	$\bar{-}$ 0.736	-0.188	$\bar{-}$ 0.479	$\bar{-}$ 0.395	1	<i>0.187</i>	<i>0.071</i>	<i>0.005</i>
Size	$\bar{-}$ 0.733	$\bar{-}$ 0.673	$\bar{-}$ 0.648	-0.018	$\bar{-}$ 0.067	0.164	0.455	1	<i>0.000</i>	<i>0.077</i>
Sorting	0.498	0.427	0.452	-0.347	0.030	0.103	$\bar{-}$ 0.592	$\bar{-}$ 0.903	1	<i>0.149</i>
ρ	$\bar{-}$ 0.960	$\bar{-}$ 0.948	$\bar{-}$ 0.985	-0.406	$\bar{-}$ 0.321	$\bar{-}$ 0.207	0.810	0.584	-0.492	1

*p = 0.000 corresponds to $p < 0.005$ (strong correlation)

Table 4

Factor loadings of radiological variables on three significant principal components. Percentage of variance explained by each principal component and their cumulative percentage of total variance are also given.

Variables	PC1	PC2	PC3
²²⁶ Ra	0.46	0.09	-0.19
²³² Th	0.45	0.14	-0.26
⁴⁰ K	0.46	0.13	-0.18
²¹⁰ Pb _{ex}	0.13	0.61	0.75
Size	-0.27	0.56	-0.21
Sorting	0.30	-0.50	0.51
Bulk density	-0.45	-0.11	0.05
% of Variance	65.3	29.5	3.9
Cumulative %	65.3	94.8	98.7